

Effect of Compensation, Work Motivation and Work Discipline on Employee Performance of Zulu Alpha Papa Company

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ABSTRACT: Representative execution is a determinant of the advancement or decay of an organization, worker execution is impacted by a few variables including remuneration factors, inspiration factors, and work discipline factors, from these components we can see the organization's usefulness, since representative execution will be straightforwardly corresponding to organization efficiency, on the off chance that representative execution expands, organization usefulness additionally increments, despite what might be expected assuming worker execution diminishes, organization efficiency likewise diminishes. The reason for this examination was to decide how the impact of pay, inspiration, and work discipline on worker execution at PT. Zulu Alpha Papa. This examination strategy utilizing subjective techniques with the number of tests utilized in this investigation were 120 respondents who were disseminated haphazardly to representatives of the PT. Zap head office. Inspecting strategy utilizing soaked example while information examination utilizing way investigation procedure (Path Model) which is upheld by Smart PLS programming variant 3.0. Because of this examination, the outcomes showed that there was a positive and huge impact among pay and worker execution, there was a positive and huge impact of inspiration on representative execution, there was a positive and huge impact of work discipline on worker execution, remuneration, inspiration, work discipline at the same time had a positive impact and important to worker execution.

KEYWORDS: Compensation, Employee Performance, Work Motivation, and Work Discipline

I. INTRODUCTION

In the current period of globalization, organizations need to frame a quality labor force for the existence of the organization. A few things that influence an organization to accomplish a specific objective are additionally expanding. Changes in the business climate have caused individuals to understand the significance of HR as a wellspring of the authoritative upper hand. In this manner, HR with higher abilities are considered equipped for supporting the significance of representative execution. Execution is an aftereffect of work in conduct that has been accomplished in finishing the jobs and duties given in a specific period (Kasmir, 2015). In execution that contains norms that should be met, so the individuals who accomplish the guidelines set are acceptable or the other way around for the individuals who are not accomplished, less great or bad. The job of innovation has started to initiate the job of HR. In any case, HR is as yet expected to prop the innovation they have. Accordingly, it isn't shocking that the mix of the two outcomes in tremendous benefits for the organization. Since regardless of how complex the innovation is, you need human administrations to move it. This implies that the job of people can't completely use any innovation, and the job of innovation will just progress and talk about the work they get

The magnificence center business is right now a diva in Indonesia, the expansion of excellence facilities is the primary fascination for PT. Zulu Alpha Papa magnificence facility to breath life into the market in the business. An organization that has a dream of "working on the personal satisfaction locally through wellbeing and excellence" Established in 2009 up to this point PT. Zulu Alpha Papa, otherwise called ZAP Clinic, has 49 branches spread all through Indonesia, by joining the idea of ZAP Health and Hospitality center administrations into a Clinic that guarantees dependability, best innovation in its group. Not just serving wellbeing items and magnificence items, right now ZAP likewise assumes a functioning part in advancing wellbeing administrations like immunizations for grown-ups and kids, as an answer for ceaselessly work on the personal satisfaction. Lately, the decrease in benefits experienced by the ZAP center affects the government assistance of each representative, there is no compensation change which makes a cascading type of influence on the presentation of representatives, representatives are more averse to work at work

with the goal that their work discipline diminishes. This marvel is in accordance with the ZAP Clinic Performance Key Performance Index accomplished by each representative who has not had the option to meet the assumptions set by the organization in 2018 and 2019. At the point when worker execution decreases, it will influence work inspiration and furthermore representative work discipline, it can be seen from representative participation information. In worker participation information in 2017, 2018, 2019 participation information for representatives who are missing in one year arrived at 40%, as such, workers don't have a high familiarity with work discipline. With the decrease in worker execution it will influence the organization's exhibition, in the drawn out the organization's failure to give pay enhancements will hurt the actual organization. Representatives work less energetically and will influence the nature of the items created and this will affect client support will move to different organizations that offer better item quality, it doesn't stop there with a lessening in worker resolve and inspiration will affect worker work discipline, when a worker doesn't do to accomplish the work then he will go about however he sees fit assuming a representative accomplishes the work as per his will, the representative isn't as per the organization's principles he acts with his own norms, this will be an awful impact for the organization. In this way the variables that influence the exhibition of representatives at PT. Zulu Alpha Papa should be fixed promptly to have the option to further develop worker execution with the goal that the organization's efficiency can be kept up with. By believing that to have the option to investigate this examination, the title "Impact Of Compensation, Motivation and Work Discipline on the Performance of Employees of Pt. Zulu Alpha Papa".

II. THEORY STUDY

1. Employee Performance

Execution is the acknowledgment of the work that has been finished by the representative. The accomplishment of worker execution expects to make or accomplish the best objectives that have been set by the organization. If an individual or gathering of representatives has set norms or guidelines of achievement and set benchmarks in estimation, then, at that point execution can be perceived and estimated. In case there is no proportion of achievement, there is no chance of knowing the presence of an individual or association. Kasmir (2016: 181) contends that exhibition is the consequence of work and work conduct accomplished by representatives inside a specific timeframe to do the jobs or obligations allowed to them by the organization. As per Wilson Bangun (2012:231), execution is the consequence of somebody finishing work as per task necessities (work prerequisites). In the meantime, as indicated by the presentation of Mangkunegara (2017: 67), representatives have accomplished outcomes as far as quality and amount in doing their obligations as per the errands relegated by the organization. From the well-qualified assessment above, it tends to be inferred that presentation is an individual's abilities and capacities to accomplish the outcomes set by the organization.

2. Compensation

Compensation is a wide range of installments made by workers due to the business relationship, including monetary (direct) installments like wages, advantages, and commissions, and non-monetary installments, for example, get-away privileges and specialist's protection (circuitous). Pay is given by the organization. Representative pay incorporates monetary and non-monetary, implying that the organization will repay all workers included, and the remuneration given is for the commitments or difficult work of representatives to work for the organization (Kasmir, 2016: 233). As indicated by Ricky W. Griffin in his book, compensation is a blessing from the association to representatives as a trade-off for their work. As per Sutrisno (2016: 197), pay is a type of acknowledgment given to representatives as pay. what's more, it tends to be presumed that remuneration is the contrary consequence of utilizing laborers or administrations given by laborers to organizations or associations.

3. Motivation

Each achievement accomplished by an organization, as long as there is a major job for every representative, the increment in usefulness moved by every worker is indistinguishable from the work inspiration they have, the inspiration to give the best for the organization. As per Danang Sunyoto in Rianto (2020) examining how to support the functioning soul of a diligent employee to work preferably by giving his abilities to accomplish organizational objectives, According to Rivai in Patmawati (2018:133) inspiration is deciding individual mentalities and qualities to have the option to accomplish things. Explicit to accomplish objectives person. As indicated by Stephen P. Robbin in Busro. M. (2018) states that motivation both from the inside and from outside the individual is significant in an association that work to accomplish the objectives and targets to be accomplished. From a portion of

the assertions of the specialists above, it very well may be presumed that the reasons set forward are: a demonstration was done by a person.

4. Work Dicipline

In an organization or association, authorizing work discipline is a commitment for each representative, the presence of work discipline in every worker can guarantee the upkeep of request and the smooth execution of the organization's work, so ideal outcomes will be acquired. Discipline is a condition where somebody who is an individual from the association observes the principles set by the association deliberately. Work is a human movement to accomplish the objectives that have been arranged. Work discipline is the conduct of representatives to act as per what has been dictated by the association (Saluy and Treshia, 2018), as indicated by Mulianto (2016: 189) work discipline is characterized as commonly acknowledged standards, morals and propensities, and methodology for acting in an environment of work. also, corresponding to work. As per Hasibuan (2009: 194), essentially there are numerous pointers that influence the degree of representative discipline, including objectives, authority models, compensation, equity, oversight, lawful observers, emphatics, human relations. It very well may be presumed that work discipline is a disposition, ongoing conduct that is, for the most part, acknowledged as a standard, hardworking attitude and demeanor in the technique for acting in a climate and its relationship to work.

5. Conceptual Framework

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses quantitative methods, namely research that examines certain populations and samples and uses data from research tools to test the established hypotheses. By using a Likert scale, researchers hope to obtain great convenience in the data processing has higher reliability in classifying subjects based on perception, and is more flexible than other technologies. Applicable to various Happenings.

1. Population and Samples

The number of inhabitants in this examination were all workers of the administrative center of PT.ZAP, for the example of this investigation, were all representatives of the administrative center of PT.ZAP, which added up to 120 individuals. By utilizing an immersed test, the analyst desires to get legitimate information, the procedure for taking this example utilizes the strategy of Irregular testing by appropriating polls to workers arbitrarily. Information Collection Techniques In this examination, analysts utilized subjective information as numbers like the number of representatives, poll answer scores, and others. Kinds of information that utilized in this examination comprised of:

- a. Essential information Essential information as per Sugiyono (2014) in this examination was acquired from information sources at the exploration area by conveying surveys straightforwardly to workers of the PT.ZAP head office division and the aftereffects of the information were gathered and handled by the creator himself.

- b. Optional Data

The optional information as indicated by Sugiyono (2014) in this examination comes from writing concentrates through different diaries, showcasing magazine articles, and articles taken from the web to get the information required in this investigation.

2. Data Analysis Methods The data examination strategy as shown by Sugiyono (2014) suggests that for can examine data variables and sorts of respondents, by offering data to for each factor considered, and find out to test the hypothesis that has been submitted. Experts use the way examination strategy (Path Model) with the help of smartPLS 3.0 programming. Expressive Analysis, Expressive examination as demonstrated by Sugiyono (2014) explains that the current data without making closes, so the data is adequately accessible. Hidden Equation Modeling (SEM) Partial Least Square (PLS) According to Ghozali and Latan (2015) the justification SEM (PLS) is to make and explain the effect association between latent factors as following :
- a. Assessment Model (Outer Model) the assessment used is the assessment of the savvy worth by looking at each pointers that have a relationship with the dormant variable. The assessment model has three tests as follows:
 - 1) Convergent Validity
Test to see the stacking regard between the marker and its turn of events.
A form is announced joined authenticity if the stacking worth of the factor > 0.70 Ghozali and Latan (2015).
 - 2) Discriminant Validity
Test to see the value of cross stacking on the marker to the turn of events. An advancement is reported discriminant authenticity if the number of cross stacking pointers on the form being alluded to is more important than the amount of cross stacking markers of various creates and the amount of cross stacking of the arranged form > 0.70 Ghozali and Latan (2015).
 - 3) Reliability
This is done by looking at the Cronbach alpha characteristics and the harming characteristics. Faithful quality is communicated when the calculation of composite steadfastness and Cronbach alpha > 0.70 Ghozali and Latan (2015).
 - b. Essential Model Test (Inner Model)
Test to see the effect and association between idle variables. The essential model has three tests, specifically as follows:
 - 1) R-Square
Look by seeing the R-square worth to choose the strength of the model. The model is articulated strong when the R-Square worth is > 0.75 , moderate when the R-Square worth is > 0.50 , and > 0.25 is communicated as a weak model by Ghozali and Latan (2015).
 - 2) F-Square
Never truly out the value of the model, where the f squared worth model is communicated as 0.35 while the f squared worth is communicated > 0.15 and > 0.2 is communicated by Ghozali and Latan (2015).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Statistics Description The statistical description provides an overview of the respondent's profile, namely, age, gender, income, education, length of work, marital status. Respondents from this study were all employees of the head office of PT.ZAP, the participation rate of respondents in this study was full, meaning that the questionnaires distributed had been filled out and returned all according to the amount distributed. The following is a description of the head office employee of PT. ZAP listed in table 1. The spellbinding consequences of the 120 respondents in table 1 dependent on sex and the predominance of female specialists are 84% and seen from the evaluation of representatives who are overwhelmed by laborers matured 2030 years as much as 68%, seen from the training of workers of PT. ZAP is overwhelmed by laborers with undergrad schooling attributes as much as 44%, and deciding from the length of work representatives are overwhelmed by workers > 2 years as much as 53%.
2. Estimation Model Test Results
(Outer Model)
 - 1) Convergent Validity

Table 1. Description of employees of PT.ZAP

No	characteristics	amount	Percentage (%)
1	gender		
	-Pria	19 orang	16%
	-Wanita	101 orang	84%
2	Usia :		
	20 tahun – 30 tahun	82 orang	68%
	30 tahun – 40 tahun	37 orang	31%
	40 tahun – 50 tahun	1 orang	1%
3	Status pendidikan:	2 orang	2%
	S2	53 orang	44%
	S1	5 orang	4%
	D4	35 orang	29%
	D3	25 orang	21%
	Lain-Lain		
4	Lama bekerja		
	<1 tahun	15 orang	13%
	>2 tahun	64 orang	53%
	>5 tahun	41 orang	34%

Table 2. Outer Loadings Kompensasi

Indicator	Outer loading value
X1.1	0.764
X1.2	0.780
X1.3	0.774
X1.4	0.800
X1.5	0.760
X1.6	0.854
X1.7	0.793
X1.8	0.833
X1.9	0.814
X1.10	0.813
X1.11	0.865
X1.12	0.766

Based on the results of table 2 the results of the outer loading value show that all indicators have an outer loading value (> 0.5) so it can be concluded that all indicators of compensation variables are declared valid.

Table 3. Outer Loadings Motivation

Indicator	Outer loading value
X2.1	0.809
X2.2	0.790
X2.3	0.798
X2.4	0.801
X2.5	0.733
X2.6	0.732
X2.7	0.785
X2.8	0.741
X2.9	0.762
X2.10	0.780
X2.11	0.768
X2.12	0.768
X2.13	0.765
X2.14	0.709
X2.15	0.731
X2.16	0.761
X2.17	0.804
X2.18	0.781
X2.19	0.797
X2.20	0.707
X2.21	0.803

Based on table 3, it shows that all indicators have outer loading (> 0.5) so it can be concluded that all indicators of motivational variables are declared valid.

Table 4. Outer Loadings Work Diciplin

Indicator	Outer loading value
X3.1	0.781
X3.2	0.726
X3.3	0.731
X3.4	0.790
X3.5	0.771
X3.6	0.749
X3.7	0.811
X3.8	0.819
X3.9	0.759
X3.10	0.783

Based on Table 4, it shows that the indicator has an Outer Loading (> 0.5) so it can be concluded that all indicators of work discipline variables are declared valid

Table 5. Outer Loadings Employee Performance

Indicator	Outer loading value
Y1.1	0.789
Y1.2	0.786
Y1.3	0.763
Y1.4	0.763
Y1.5	0.798
Y1.6	0.802
Y1.7	0.736
Y1.8	0.802
Y1.9	0.749
Y1.10	0.728
Y1.11	0.807
Y1.12	0.759
Y1.13	0.774
Y1.14	0.782
Y1.15	0.780
Y1.16	0.716

Based on Table 4, it shows that all indicators have outer loading (> 0.5) so it can be concluded that all indicators of employee performance variables are declared valid.

Table 6. Result of Discriminant Validity

	Kompensasi	Motivasi	Disiplin kerja	Kinerja karyawan
X1.1	0.764	0.592	0.624	0.574
X1.2	0.780	0.538	0.431	0.438
X1.3	0.774	0.558	0.502	0.466
X1.4	0.800	0.621	0.498	0.466
X1.5	0.760	0.541	0.539	0.421
X1.6	0.854	0.642	0.546	0.591
X1.7	0.793	0.602	0.566	0.542
X1.8	0.833	0.600	0.491	0.523
X1.9	0.814	0.595	0.584	0.555
X1.10	0.813	0.570	0.383	0.503
X1.11	0.865	0.686	0.566	0.612
X1.12	0.766	0.648	0.532	0.541
X2.1	0.590	0.809	0.476	0.558
X2.2	0.600	0.790	0.534	0.486
X2.3	0.579	0.798	0.466	0.515
X2.4	0.613	0.801	0.484	0.525
X2.5	0.539	0.733	0.523	0.531
X2.6	0.485	0.732	0.531	0.402
X2.7	0.551	0.785	0.562	0.468
X2.8	0.596	0.741	0.631	0.457

X2.9	0.600	0.762	0.594	0.461
X2.10	0.690	0.780	0.486	0.450
X2.11	0.728	0.768	0.570	0.546
X2.12	0.622	0.768	0.460	0.466
X2.13	0.631	0.765	0.514	0.529
X2.14	0.591	0.709	0.493	0.428
X2.15	0.518	0.731	0.477	0.472
X2.16	0.542	0.761	0.520	0.458
X2.17	0.564	0.804	0.587	0.538
X2.18	0.517	0.781	0.523	0.585
X2.19	0.496	0.797	0.514	0.582
X2.20	0.485	0.707	0.444	0.504
X2.21	0.596	0.803	0.557	0.516
X3.1	0.535	0.478	0.781	0.493
X3.2	0.418	0.426	0.726	0.504
X3.3	0.338	0.442	0.731	0.344
X3.4	0.520	0.521	0.790	0.452
X3.5	0.471	0.492	0.771	0.421
X3.6	0.455	0.432	0.749	0.544
X3.7	0.641	0.639	0.811	0.497
X3.8	0.596	0.588	0.819	0.513
X3.9	0.608	0.646	0.759	0.475
X3.10	0.417	0.557	0.783	0.438
Y1.1	0.424	0.395	0.459	0.789
Y1.2	0.479	0.507	0.495	0.786
Y1.3	0.476	0.493	0.403	0.763
Y1.4	0.518	0.535	0.453	0.763
Y1.5	0.567	0.525	0.460	0.798
Y1.6	0.483	0.504	0.438	0.802
Y1.7	0.519	0.513	0.582	0.736
Y1.8	0.480	0.456	0.472	0.802
Y1.9	0.416	0.391	0.411	0.749
Y1.10	0.554	0.588	0.511	0.728
Y1.11	0.495	0.548	0.420	0.807
Y1.12	0.520	0.469	0.404	0.759
Y1.13	0.551	0.622	0.558	0.774
Y1.14	0.440	0.494	0.416	0.782
Y1.15	0.541	0.467	0.476	0.780
Y1.16	0.544	0.484	0.543	0.716

Based on table 6, the results of the cross loading value are said to be valid because the construct indicator in question is greater than after the elimination of stage 3 Shows that all other construct indicators. Construct fulfill Discriminant validity and declared valid where the construct indicator is greater than the other construct indicators.

3) Reliability

Table 7. Reliability Test Results

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite reliability	Description
Kompensasi	0,949	0,956	Reliability
Motivasi	0,965	0,968	Reliability
Disiplin Kerja	0,925	0,937	Reliability
Kinerja karyawan	0,955	0,959	Reliability

Based on table 7, above the calculation of Cronbach's alpha and Composite reliability all construct is declared reliable.

3. Structural Model Test Results(Inner Model)

The following is the main construct drawing for testing the structural model (inner model).

Figure 1. Model Bootstrapping

1) Analysis R²

Table 8. Results R-Square

variable	R ²	Description
Employee Performance	0,516	Medium

In table 8. It can be seen that the employee performance variable R-square value more < 0.67 (0.67 > 0.516) then it can be concluded moderate. So that it can be conclude that compensation, motivation, work discipline have an impact significant impact on employee performance.

2) Analisa F² (F Square)

Table 9. F Square Results

	Employee Performance
Compansation	0.072
Motivation	0.058
Work Dicipline	0.056

Based on Table 9. It can be concluded that Compensation, Motivation and WorkDiscipline Each work has a value of 0.072, 0.058, 0.056, all three of which have Has a medium effect on employee performance.

Table 10. Hipotesis

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values
Kompensasi -> Kinerja Karyawan	0.295	0.294	0.120	2.464	0.014
Motivasi -> Kinerja Karyawan	0.273	0.268	0.137	1.994	0.047
Disiplin Kerja -> Kinerja Karyawan	0.235	0.248	0.105	2.238	0.026

Seen in table 10. It can be concluded that the results of the research model hypothesis testing:

- 1) Hypothesis 1 Compensation for Employee Performance Compensation has a t-statistic value of 2.464 > 1.96, p-value 0.014 < 0.05 and original sample 0.295, so H1 is accepted, meaning that compensation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.
- 2) Hypothesis 2 Motivation on Employee Performance Motivation has a t-statistic value of 1994 > 1.96, p-value 0.047 < 0.05 and original sample 0.273, then H2 is accepted, meaning that motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.
- 3) Hypothesis 3 Work Discipline on Employee Performance Work Discipline has a t-statistic value of 2.238 > 1.96, p-value 0.026 < 0.05 and original sample 0.235, then H3 is accepted, meaning that Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance
- 4) Hypothesis 4 Compensation, Motivation and Work Discipline simultaneously have a significant effect on Employee Performance.

$$F_{hit} = \frac{R^2(n - k - 1)}{(1 - R^2)k}$$

$$F_{hit} = \frac{0.516(120 - 3 - 1)}{(1 - 0.516)3}$$

$$F_{hit} = \frac{59.86}{1.45} = 41.223$$

$$F_{tabel} = F_{\alpha}(K, n-k, 1) = F_{0,05}(3, 120-3-1) = F_{0,05}(3, 116) = 2.680 \text{ (diperoleh dari Tabel F)}$$

Simultaneous significant test results can be seen in the calculation results. The F test was carried out to determine the effect of the variable Compensation, Motivation and Work Discipline on Employee Performance simultaneously. For testing with F . test adalah dengan membandingkan antara nilai Ftabel dengan Fhitung. Nilai Fhitung sebesar 41.223, Ftabel adalah 2.680 (lihat pada Tabel F), dengan demikian didapat hasil F hitung (41.223) > Ftabel (2.680) maka H₄ diterima. Dapat disimpulkan bahwa variabel Kompensasi, Motivasi dan Disiplin Kerja secara bersama-sama berpengaruh positif dan signifikan terhadap Kinerja Karyawan.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTION

Conclusions

1) Effect of Compensation on Employee Performance Pay basically affects laborer execution, inferring that changes of the value of compensation unidirectionally influence changes in delegate execution or thusly if pay extends there will be an extension in specialist execution levels, sensible compensation transforms into a lift for agents to have the choice to give their best potential to the association so laborers can chip away at their show to assemble association convenience. 2) The Influence of Motivation on Employee Performance Motivation impacts laborer execution, inferring that if motivation works, there will be an extension in agent execution levels since motivation is a condition that moves people towards explicit destinations and targets, motivation furthermore braces direct and gives direction to act to keep endeavouring, so that by growing work motivation for delegates will really need to enliven improvement and work inventiveness of each delegate to have the choice to fabricate the ability of each agent to achieve most outrageous helpfulness of each delegate. 3) Work Discipline on Employee Performance Work discipline basically affects agent execution, suggesting that changes of the value of work discipline straightforwardly influence changes in specialist execution or all things considered if work discipline works there will be an addition in delegate execution levels considering the way that by approving work discipline in associations or affiliations will really need to guarantee the help of solicitation and work execution, by practicing discipline in the work will make a brilliant air and can stimulate every agent to act and go about according to the applicable ethics in the association. By executing work discipline, agents will easily achieve the targets set by the association. For what reason would that be, through finishing work discipline, every agent is expected to go along and complete things according to the rules and heading of the association to make achieving the destinations set by the 4) Effect of Compensation, Motivation, Work Discipline on Employee Performance Simultaneously on Employee Performance. Remuneration, Motivation, and Work Discipline together have a positive and huge impact on Employee Performance. In the articulation above it very well may be presumed that by giving appropriate remuneration, it will actually want to invigorate and inspire workers to further develop their presence on the grounds that the pay they expect is straightforwardly relative to what the organization gives them it will make representatives persuaded to give their best potential in themselves to the organization, with great inspiration will likewise bring issues to light of every worker to consent to the guidelines set by the organization so that request and request are made inside the organization so it can make it simpler for the organization to accomplish shared objectives.

Suggestion

The end got from this exploration is that there is a positive and huge impact between remuneration on representative execution, there is a positive and huge impact between inspirations on worker execution, there is a positive and huge impact between work discipline on worker execution, and pay, inspiration, discipline factors. Cooperate has a positive and critical impact on representative execution. The creator passes on a few ideas that are displayed to the PT.Zap Company and a few upgrades for additional examination: 1) By taking a gander at the most elevated Loading Factor result is immediate remuneration, the organization should focus harder on pay from its representatives, by making a decent play structure making the pay framework understood, in case there be treachery as far as to pay, representatives who have a substantial responsibility and duties should get pay as per their responsibility and obligations. 2) Companies should fabricate agreeable participation among representatives and representatives, representatives and bosses, etc to make a warm air among workers, and every pioneer should have the option to clarify crafted by his subordinates plainly and indeed, so his subordinates can get what they need the pioneer. 3) To help the organization's objectives to accomplish the organization's vision and mission of all representatives of PT. Zap is required to run a solid authoritative culture in order to make workers with uprightness and polished methodology. 4) In request to work on the presentation of PT.Zap representatives, the organization is required to have the option to give or include its representatives in workshops or gathering training to work on the capacities of workers, by partaking in these training representatives are accepted to be inspired to give their latent capacity. 5) The

quantity of respondents in this examination is restricted with the goal that specialists expect further exploration to expand respondents to get more substantial outcomes and analysts just utilize the factors of remuneration, inspiration, work discipline, and worker execution, ideally for the examination can utilize different factors identified with representative execution.

REFERENCES

1. A.A. Anwar Prabu Mangkunegara. (2017). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*.
2. *Perusahaan Remaja Rosdakarya*. Bandung.
3. Bangun, Wilson. (2012). "Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia". Erlangga. Jakarta.
4. Dewi Patmawati dan Realize. (2018). The Effect Of Motivation and Dicipline Toward Performance Of Employee On PT. Perempurna Readymix Concrete. E-Jurnal Apresiasi Ekonomi Volume 6, E-ISSN 2613 – 9774. Indonesia.
5. Edy, Sutrisno. (2016). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*, Kencana Prenada Media Group. Jakarta.
6. Ghozali, dan Latan. (2015). *Partial Least Squares: Konsep, Teknik dan Aplikasi Menggunakan Program SmartPLS 3.0*. Badan Penerbit UNDIP. Semarang.
7. Ghozali, Imam. (2006). *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate Dengan Program SPSS*. Universitas Diponegoro. Semarang.
8. Ghozali, Imam. (2011). *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate dengan Program IBM SPSS*. Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro. Semarang
9. Griffin, Ricky W. (2004). *Manajemen*. Jilid 1. Erlangga. Jakarta.
10. Hasibuan. (2010). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Bumi Aksara. Jakarta.
11. Kasmir, (2016). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Rajawali Pers. Depok.
12. Muliando, Sindu, Cahyadi, Eko R., Widjayakusuma, M. Karebet. (2006). *Panduan Lengkap Supervisi*
13. *Diperkaya Perspektif Syariah*. PT Gramedia. Jakarta.
14. Rivai, Veithzal. (2011). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia untuk Perusahaan PT Remaja Rosdakarya*. Bandung.
15. Robbins, Stephen. P. (2006). *Organizational Behavior*. Indonesian edition. Gramedia. Jakarta.
16. Riyanto, S, Thamrin, M. (2020). The Effect of Work Motivation, Work Enviroment, and Work life Balance on Employee Performance at PT. Angkasa Pura I (Persero) Sultan Aji Muhammad Sulaiman Sepinggan Airport – Balikpapan. IOSR Journal of Dental and Medical Sciences (IOSRJDMS), E-ISSN: 2279-0853, P-ISSN: 2279-0861. 19(6), 40-47. Indonesia.
17. Saluy, AB, Treshia, Y. (2018), Pengaruh motivasi kerja, disiplin kerja dan kompensasi terhadap kinerja karyawan (Studi Kasus di Perusahaan PT IE). *Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen dan Bisnis*, 2 (1), 53-70. Indonesia.
18. Sugiyono. (2014). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif dan Kualitatif dan R&D*. Alfabeta. Bandung.

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